

Dendrochronological analysis of the timbers of Barcode ship 4 (BC04), from Barcode, Oslo.

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Samples from ship 4, found during excavations at Barcode in Oslo, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis in January 2015. A total of 17 boats were found and excavated at Barcode in Oslo over the past several years, and these are currently the subject of ongoing dendrochronological analysis (for example Daly 2010a&b, 2011c). Most of the Barcode boats are dating to the second half of the 16th century, but with one exception – BC17 is earlier (Daly 2013c&e).

All the samples described in this report are of *Quercus sp.*, oak.

		Z119001a	Z119004a	Z119008a	Z119006a	Z119002a	Z119007a	Z119005a	Z119003a
	Z119001a	*	\	1,94	\	1,67	\	2,56	\
	Z119004a	\	*	4,43	1,59	1,9	\	1,75	2,44
Average Z119M001	Z119008a	1,94	4,43	*	3,89	4,89	4,32	2,99	-
	Z119006a	\	1,59	3,89	*	6,93	7,32	4,65	1,09
	Z119002a	1,67	1,9	4,89	6,93	*	8,92	7,1	2,73
	Z119007a	\	\	4,32	7,32	8,92	*	4,82	-
	Z119005a	2,56	1,75	2,99	4,65	7,1	4,82	*	4,41
	Z119003a	\	2,44	-	1,09	2,73	-	4,41	*

Table 1. Barcode ship BC04, Oslo. Internal correlation (t-value) for the samples from the boat. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

In the interest of open access to data and to enable researchers to utilise this material in the future, the measurements are printed in the catalogue. All measurements will also be submitted to the Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology (DCCD, www.dendrochronology.eu). For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t-value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

Fig. 1. Barcode ship BC04, Oslo. Diagram showing the chronological position of the tree-ring curves from the timbers from the boat.

BC04

A core from the keel of Barcode ship BC04 was analysed dendrochronologically previously and the tree used to make it was found to have been felled after AD 1437 (Daly 2014). Seven more samples have now been analysed and all these are dated.

The tree-ring curves from five of the samples, all planks from the boat, match well together (table 1) and are averaged to form a single tree-ring curve (Z119M001) of 257 years in length. This curve is dated and covers the period AD 1317-1573. Of the samples from these five planks only one (x082) has sapwood preserved.

Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that was used to make this plank is estimated to be c. AD 1572-86. This might be taken as the date for the felling of the majority of the timbers for the boat, marked in green in fig 1.

As can be seen in table 1, there is not strong correlation between the tree-ring curves from the group of five planks and the remaining timbers from the boat. This might indicate that they are from a different source than the main group. Twelve sapwood rings are preserved on one of these samples (x065). Again allowing for missing sapwood, the estimated felling date for the tree that plank x065 was made from is c. AD 1597-1605, marked in blue in the illustration (fig. 1). This might indicate that later additions or repairs were made on the boat, some c. 20 years after the first building phase.

To estimate the felling date of the trees used for the boat a sapwood statistic for Norway is used. Oaks here have, on average, 15 (-8 +6) sapwood years (Christensen & Havemann 1998).

Filenames	-	-	Z119M001	
-	start	dates	AD1317	
-	dates	end	AD1573	
q415029m04	AD1356	AD1540	11,83	Evangelistas altarpiece Seville Cathedral 29 planks West Swedish oak imports (Marta Domínguez pers comm)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	11,31	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
EP41592	AD1390	AD1592	10,17	Stirling Castle Scotland Scandinavian imports (Crone pers comm)
B028M003	AD1386	AD1576	9,07	Køge Havn 4 timbers (Daly 2013g)
Z073m001	AD1385	AD1574	8,86	Barcode boat 14 3 timbers (Daly 2011c)
2121M002	AD1052	AD1596	8,82	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001b)
JUTLAND6	AD846	AD1793	8,60	Jutland (Daly unpubl.)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	8,59	B&W vrag 2 (Daly 2000b)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	8,18	Sjælland (Daly unpubl)
Z040M001	AD1386	AD1567	8,09	Gåsehage Randers 2 timbers (Daly 2009b)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	8,03	Ålborg østerå + boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a & 2001a)
Z089m001	AD1399	AD1581	7,62	Barcode skib 5 9 timbers (Daly 2013a)
SM100003	AD1135	AD1711	6,94	Ystad (Bartholin pers comm)
midtjy17	AD536	AD1980	6,89	midtjylland (Christensen pers comm)
B0275Morange2	AD1331	AD1557	6,82	Gammel Strand CPH import timber (Daly forthcoming)
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	6,49	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group (Daly 1998c)
4077M00Z re...	AD1310	AD1546	6,32	Nyborg Slot Renaissance phase 38 timbers (Daly 2007)

Table 2. Barcode ship BC04, Oslo, average of 5 planks. Result of the correlation between average curve from five planks and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	X058 Z119003a	X065 Z119004a	
-	start	dates	AD1454	AD1511	
-	dates	end	AD1560	AD1596	
Z109M001	AD1437	AD1597	7,08	4,66	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013f)
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	6,57	4,33	SNorway ships 63 timbers (Daly unpubl.)
Z110M001	AD1342	AD1601	5,28	3,36	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013f)
barcode all...	AD1418	AD1587	5,21	6,15	barcode all ships 15 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z086M001	AD1468	AD1584	5,09	-	Havnelageret 1 boat 3 timbers (Daly 2012)
Z0307M01	AD1435	AD1585	4,82	5,74	Barcode ship BC07 5 timbers (Daly 2010c)
Z0302M01	AD1429	AD1587	-	5,03	Barcode B 11-13 BC02 2 timbers (Daly 2010b)
4077M001	AD1310	AD1540	4,81	-	Nyborg slot (Daly 1999)
Z065M003	AD1355	AD1617	4,68	-	Bjørvika Kenneth Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2011b)
Z118M002	AD1422	AD1636	4,46	4,61	Paléhaven I Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2014)
006526M1	AD1357	AD1578	4,26	3,58	B&W vrag 2 (Daly 2000b)
JUTLAND 6	AD846	AD1793	4,06	3,82	Jutland (Daly unpubl.)
Z0306M01	AD1418	AD1585	3,68	4,16	Barcode 6 6 timbers (Daly 2010a)
Z0302M04	AD1407	AD1591	3,01	4,83	BC02 6 timbers (Daly 2014)
Z0302M03	AD1407	AD1590	-	4,68	Barcode ship 02 BC02 4 planks (Daly 2014)
Z0309M01	AD1395	AD1561	-	4,28	Barcode ship BC09 2 timbers (Daly 2010d)
Z094M001	AD1465	AD1650	-	4,44	Portørenga Norge 3 timbers (Daly 2013b)

Table 3. Barcode ship BC04, Oslo, two planks. Result of the correlation between tree-ring curve from two planks and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

The correlation between the average curve from the five planks that form the main group and a range of site and master chronologies for Northern Europe is shown in table 2. The highest correlation is achieved with a chronology from west Sweden, and with chronologies from other sites, that have been shown, through dendrochronological analysis, to be of west Swedish imports. The results strongly suggest that the main timber group for BC04 grew in West Sweden.

The correlation values for the tree-ring curves from the two remaining planks (x058 & x065) are shown in table 3. These two planks are dated using tree-ring data chiefly from other boat finds in the Oslo area. Although it is difficult to pinpoint a precise source for the trees that these two planks are made from, the results might point to a source in the wider Oslo fjord region.

Filenames	-	-	Keel Z119001a	
-	start	dates	AD1352	
-	dates	end	AD1429	
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	6,29	Kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group (Daly 1998c)
Z096M001	AD1378	AD1517	5,82	Bispevika 2 (short) (Daly 2013d)
2119M001	AD1361	AD1471	5,72	Ejby Kirke (Daly 1998a)
Z0350029	AD1199	AD1470	5,46	Gedserbrogård skibsplanke (Daly 2009a)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	5,33	Sjælland (Daly unpubl.)
8113M001	AD1350	AD1440	5,20	Mårup Kirke (Daly 1998b)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	5,04	Klim Strandvraget (Daly 2011a)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	4,65	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
2136M001	AD1360	AD1473	4,59	Næstved. Det Gamle Rådhus (Daly 2000c)
LS103M01	AD1359	AD1489	4,46	Skørby Torn (Lund Uni. Revised Daly 2007)
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	4,44	Skaane / Blekinge (Lund Universitet)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	4,43	Ålborg østerå + boulevarden (Daly 2000a & 2001a)
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	4,37	Fenton Tower Scotland Norwegian imports (Crone pers comm)
Z027M002	AD1313	AD1567	4,22	Amager Strand Vrag (Daly 2008)
0059m001	AD1264	AD1434	4,12	Vedby Hage vrag (Daly & Eriksen 1996)

Table 4. Barcode ship BC04, Oslo, keel. Result of the correlation between tree-ring curve from the keel and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

The correlation between the tree-ring curve from the keel sample and a range of site and master chronologies for Northern Europe (table 4), suggests that the tree that was used for this keel grew in Southern Norway or western coastal Sweden.

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Catalogue

Catalogue format:

Filename
Title and sample number
Tree species (QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak, PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine, PCAB = <i>Picea abies</i> , spruce) and number of years measured
Chronological position of the tree-ring curve
Number of sapwood years, presence of bark
Felling date
The measurements start at the innermost preserved ring

BC04

Z119001a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtadel x088 keel prøve x266

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 78 years length

Dated AD1352 to AD1429

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 131.83 Sensitivity 0.15

Interpretation after AD1437

97	159	117	140	152	110	92	87	102	71
92	115	146	131	145	150	125	118	135	198
158	153	199	162	159	127	135	164	154	124
124	130	163	133	136	151	138	122	112	84
91	111	108	117	112	116	131	138	122	160
104	105	104	154	151	128	147	133	163	170
180	192	148	136	106	139	103	118	115	132
118	131	131	101	104	154	145	155		

Z119002a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtadel x046 hudbord x300

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 208 years length

Dated AD1366 to AD1573

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 120.51 Sensitivity 0.22

Interpretation after AD1581

137	140	236	194	137	172	189	158	271	138
78	85	143	192	200	204	168	243	177	134
192	110	76	127	186	131	120	211	120	87
132	171	186	205	224	237	200	148	242	249
210	170	202	205	207	188	207	175	88	110
103	128	136	110	141	149	176	143	158	213
142	164	149	239	183	160	260	188	170	100
96	141	89	80	111	153	143	133	132	172
115	152	166	134	103	102	78	55	70	74
116	135	122	140	106	89	72	51	67	75
105	143	134	129	110	73	80	72	97	85
88	62	84	92	70	62	118	123	111	115
113	156	117	69	71	58	47	69	81	88
108	89	89	49	87	129	119	99	96	147
141	163	174	164	146	154	151	141	103	65
68	64	51	65	53	51	76	69	74	105
118	116	119	93	111	71	68	57	75	63
67	102	122	169	159	98	93	110	110	91
55	45	72	57	59	107	79	78	81	69
58	55	53	60	99	108	133	121	116	106
59	59	51	52	61	73	100	80		

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Z119003a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båt del x058 hudbord x301

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 107 years length

Dated AD1454 to AD1560

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 84.57 Sensitivity 0.14

Interpretation after AD1568

93	115	117	82	84	78	79	69	84	85
72	98	79	89	121	74	88	84	142	124
102	98	120	89	100	102	108	117	117	93
90	99	79	86	95	83	99	89	81	103
81	73	71	78	63	51	46	72	88	80
84	87	84	118	98	109	106	99	95	86
79	63	87	86	63	73	73	79	64	61
63	105	106	76	102	80	86	81	75	69
65	78	57	60	80	99	73	70	83	72
91	90	82	82	81	65	69	83	74	75
70	79	72	62	65	63	62			

Z119004a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båt del x065 hudbord x302

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 86 years length

Dated AD1511 to AD1596

12 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 105.09 Sensitivity 0.19

Interpretation AD1597-1605

197	178	178	137	173	150	125	149	102	95
131	141	87	89	113	124	84	69	102	121
91	101	86	78	96	91	81	105	128	105
110	106	117	105	108	94	90	121	58	71
115	107	128	91	87	106	95	107	112	77
119	100	91	118	113	92	108	117	64	73
94	114	119	160	124	132	133	101	86	72
110	116	89	119	99	92	60	74	73	57
79	88	86	76	84	94				

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Z119005a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båt del x082 hudbord x305

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 249 years length

Dated AD1317 to AD1565

0 sapwood rings but h/s boundary present

Average ring width 97.82 Sensitivity 0.19

Interpretation AD1572-86

214	147	230	245	247	245	359	272	308	194
214	175	83	116	154	180	104	109	151	184
177	216	193	163	198	163	102	123	173	129
145	148	138	87	118	100	134	148	151	169
86	63	47	49	63	70	105	126	128	147
141	166	112	111	82	77	98	138	66	44
48	70	96	109	156	139	105	122	91	74
82	53	47	54	50	40	63	56	38	43
53	71	77	104	96	104	85	114	116	112
92	102	87	98	112	132	140	102	66	55
71	75	76	57	53	84	70	71	74	70
74	71	71	73	64	82	65	77	67	61
82	66	61	78	64	66	62	47	53	58
58	63	61	61	57	47	41	41	65	64
59	73	74	69	59	48	49	46	59	74
75	122	58	48	45	48	35	32	31	49
37	57	53	36	40	58	51	70	90	154
134	127	114	87	59	44	48	47	65	71
73	70	48	45	110	96	84	85	123	106
153	158	132	145	153	133	130	91	107	123
94	76	91	77	95	110	95	106	151	127
150	135	137	129	73	92	84	69	75	98
141	126	143	110	96	103	105	86	63	71
82	92	102	114	170	107	117	70	63	67
48	51	62	93	80	59	71	80	81	

Z119006a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båt del x111 hudbord x306

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 135 years length

Dated AD1429 to AD1563

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 129.73 Sensitivity 0.22

Interpretation after AD1571

228	157	131	195	182	251	110	113	107	125
137	171	153	198	163	179	216	142	233	172
153	138	137	88	93	98	167	160	191	141
157	98	86	54	53	73	71	67	92	101
91	82	65	79	51	104	98	135	82	110
68	82	49	86	117	80	91	123	151	82
89	56	71	67	103	104	118	132	118	103
72	104	92	96	112	126	160	148	170	149
144	171	198	167	141	152	109	123	107	67
118	124	180	166	135	144	182	200	230	188
164	185	97	85	95	96	123	182	160	164
214	172	143	149	156	121	115	117	109	195
138	137	179	152	128	120	97	95	72	113
95	183	148	155	216					

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Z119007a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båt del x126 hudbord x307

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 102 years length

Dated AD1403 to AD1504

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 160.43 Sensitivity 0.20

Interpretation after AD1512

201	265	303	292	292	250	335	274	228	254
215	112	132	138	211	226	166	218	175	179
198	196	183	168	243	167	233	200	159	207
183	194	121	141	154	171	151	222	225	214
164	178	200	197	213	229	209	160	113	116
90	87	146	161	156	135	209	137	125	81
86	99	80	127	138	136	151	82	84	90
74	143	131	146	99	151	125	113	83	125
139	112	136	195	180	117	101	93	92	70
118	128	145	142	122	109	85	125	185	157
124	124								

Z119008a

Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båt del x076 hudbord x308

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 163 years length

Dated AD1400 to AD1562

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 118.33 Sensitivity 0.23

Interpretation after AD1569

237	253	264	218	276	190	253	169	172	200
188	153	182	232	60	75	64	77	95	94
100	97	101	64	170	82	72	142	117	123
96	100	156	148	133	151	100	110	106	113
162	97	99	118	113	141	68	98	98	107
103	139	128	123	99	136	112	110	135	129
98	111	128	132	149	149	141	120	89	105
86	75	64	84	159	112	105	93	156	165
118	55	111	113	146	98	119	143	122	105
83	67	131	105	109	106	99	104	104	88
98	157	110	88	94	130	134	150	140	146
119	124	126	119	125	64	84	64	78	63
59	77	117	64	67	105	98	117	93	84
87	90	148	60	48	108	119	122	105	116
103	91	105	122	96	129	99	147	180	68
71	135	122	123	115	102	148	70	100	133
125	171	141							

4th May 2015

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	Conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	Interpretation / felling
	BC04										
Z119001a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x088 keel prøve x266	78	AD1352	AD1429	core	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1437
Z119002a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x046 hodbord x300	208	AD1366	AD1573	R	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1581
Z119003a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x058 hodbord x301	107	AD1454	AD1560	T	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1568
Z119004a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x065 hodbord x302	86	AD1511	AD1596	T	G	12	N	N	S1	AD1597-1605
Z119005a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x082 hodbord x305	249	AD1317	AD1565	T	G	0	B	N	S1	AD1572-86
Z119006a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x111 hodbord x306	135	AD1429	AD1563	T	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1571
Z119007a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x126 hodbord x307	102	AD1403	AD1504	T	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1512
Z119008a	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo båtde1 x076 hodbord x308	163	AD1400	AD1562	R	G	0	N	N	N	after AD1569
Z119M001	Barcode ship 04 BC04 NMM03010084 Oslo hodbord 5 timber mean	257	AD1317	AD1573							
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			24 April 2015								